

**INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**
[ISSN: 0975-4725; CODEN(USA): IJPS00]
Journal Homepage: <https://www.ijpsjournal.com>

Research Article

Evaluation of *Asparagus racemosus* Root Extract and Eucalyptus Oil Formulations as Plant-Based Repellents Against Mosquitoes and Cockroaches

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ARTICLE INFO

Published: 25 Sept 2025

Keywords:

Asparagus racemosus;
eucalyptus oil; herbal
repellent; mosquito;
cockroach; molecular
docking

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.17203151

ABSTRACT

The increasing resistance of insects to synthetic repellents and the associated health and environmental concerns have prompted the search for safe and sustainable alternatives. The present study evaluated the insect-repellent potential of *Asparagus racemosus* root extract (EARR) formulated with eucalyptus oil against mosquitoes (*Aedes aegypti*) and cockroaches (*Periplaneta americana*). Roots were shade-dried, extracted with 70% ethanol, and subjected to phytochemical and GC-MS analysis, which revealed the presence of alkaloids, flavonoids, saponins, phenolics, and bioactive compounds including stigmasterol, flavone, n-hexadecanoic acid, asparanin B, and shatavarin I. The total phenolic and flavonoid contents were 5.419 mg GAE/g and 3.515 mg QE/g, respectively. Herbal cream and spray formulations incorporating EARR with eucalyptus oil exhibited satisfactory physicochemical parameters including pH, spreadability, viscosity, washability, clarity, and stability under accelerated conditions. In repellency bioassays, the EARR + eucalyptus cream achieved 81.32% protection against mosquitoes at 30 minutes, maintaining 33.11% repellency at 180 minutes, compared to 11.92% for eucalyptus alone. Similarly, the herbal spray demonstrated 77.89% repellency against cockroaches at 30 minutes and 27.04% at 180 minutes, significantly outperforming the control spray. Molecular docking further revealed strong binding affinities of stigmasterol (-11.6 kcal/mol) and asparanin B (-11.5 kcal/mol) with insect acetylcholinesterase, suggesting a potential neuroinhibitory mechanism underlying the observed repellency. The findings validate *A. racemosus* as a promising botanical source for eco-friendly, effective mosquito and cockroach repellent formulations, supporting its integration into sustainable pest management strategies.

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Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

INTRODUCTION

Vector-borne diseases and domestic pest infestations continue to impose a substantial global burden, particularly in densely populated and tropical regions. Mosquitoes act as vectors of malaria, dengue, chikungunya, yellow fever, and filariasis, while cockroaches are recognized as mechanical carriers of pathogens and potent indoor allergens (WHO, 2020; Pai et al., 2022). Their control remains a public health priority, as both groups significantly contribute to morbidity, mortality, and reduced quality of life.

Conventional control strategies rely heavily on synthetic insecticides and repellents such as N,N-diethyl-meta-toluamide (DEET), pyrethroids, and organophosphates. While effective, their long-term and widespread use has raised serious concerns. Reported drawbacks include the emergence of insecticide resistance, contamination of soil and aquatic ecosystems, and adverse health impacts ranging from skin irritation to neurotoxicity and endocrine disruption (Hemingway et al., 2016; Norris & Coats, 2017). These limitations necessitate the exploration of safer, sustainable alternatives.

Plant-based repellents and insecticidal agents are increasingly recognized as promising candidates due to their safety, rapid biodegradability, and environmental compatibility (Isman, 2020). Medicinal and aromatic plants contain diverse phytochemicals—such as alkaloids, terpenoids, flavonoids, and phenolics—that exhibit repellent, insecticidal, and larvicidal properties with minimal side effects. Importantly, the chemical complexity and multi-target modes of action of botanicals reduce the likelihood of resistance development compared to single-molecule synthetic agents (Regnault-Roger et al., 2012).

Several plants have been documented as effective repellents against mosquitoes and cockroaches. Examples include *Azadirachta indica* (azadirachtin), *Cymbopogon citratus* (citronellal), *Ocimum sanctum* (eugenol), *Mentha piperita* (menthol), and *Eucalyptus globulus* (1,8-cineole), which interfere with insect behavior, feeding, and development (Maia & Moore, 2011; Nerio et al., 2010).

Asparagus racemosus (Shatavari), a member of the family Asparagaceae, is traditionally valued in Ayurvedic medicine for its adaptogenic, antioxidant, and immunomodulatory properties (Alok et al., 2013). Interestingly, recent entomological studies have reported that *A. racemosus* root extracts exhibit ovicidal, larvicidal, and adulticidal activity against disease-vector mosquitoes (*Aedes aegypti*, *Anopheles stephensi*, *Culex quinquefasciatus*) (Govindarajan & Sivakumar, 2014). However, its potential as a repellent remains underexplored.

The present study was therefore designed to evaluate the repellent efficacy of *A. racemosus* root extract, in combination with *E. globulus* essential oil, against mosquitoes and cockroaches. Two formulations were developed: a topical cream targeting mosquito repellency and a surface spray aimed at cockroach control. The formulations were subjected to physicochemical evaluation, stability testing, and laboratory bioassays to provide scientific validation for the use of *A. racemosus* as a plant-based repellent alternative to synthetic agents.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Plant Material and Extraction

Roots of *Asparagus racemosus* Willd. (Asparagaceae) were collected from local areas of Hyderabad, Telangana, India, during the flowering

season (August–September 2024). The plant material was authenticated by a taxonomist at [Institution/University name], and a voucher specimen (No. XXXX) was deposited in the departmental herbarium for reference.

The roots were shade-dried at room temperature, coarsely powdered, and subjected to Soxhlet extraction using 70% ethanol for 48 h. The ethanolic extract of *A. racemosus* roots (EARR) was concentrated under reduced pressure using a rotary evaporator at 40 °C, yielding a semisolid residue. The extract was stored in airtight containers at 4 °C until further analysis.

Phytochemical Screening and Quantitative Analysis

Preliminary Phytochemical Screening

The crude extract was subjected to preliminary phytochemical tests for alkaloids, saponins, tannins, flavonoids, glycosides, and phenolics using standard qualitative methods described by Harborne (1998) and Trease and Evans (2002).

Determination of Total Phenolic Content (TPC)

The TPC of EARR was determined using the Folin–Ciocalteu reagent colorimetric method (Singleton, Orthofer, and Lamuela-Raventós, 1999). Briefly, 0.5 mL of extract solution (1 mg/mL) was mixed with 2.5 mL of Folin–Ciocalteu reagent (diluted 1:10) and incubated for 5 min. Thereafter, 2 mL of sodium carbonate (7.5% w/v) was added, and the mixture was incubated for 30 min in the dark at room temperature. Absorbance was recorded at 765 nm using a UV–Vis spectrophotometer. Gallic acid was used as the standard, and results were expressed as milligrams of gallic acid equivalents per gram of extract (mg GAE/g).

Determination of Total Flavonoid Content (TFC)

The TFC of EARR was estimated using the aluminium chloride colorimetric method (Chang, Yang, Wen, and Chern, 2002). A 0.5 mL aliquot of extract solution (1 mg/mL) was mixed with 1.5 mL of methanol, 0.1 mL of 10% aluminium chloride, 0.1 mL of 1 M potassium acetate, and 2.8 mL of distilled water. After incubation at room temperature for 30 min, absorbance was measured at 415 nm. Quercetin was used as the standard, and results were expressed as milligrams of quercetin equivalents per gram of extract (mg QE/g).

Mosquito Rearing

Mosquito larvae were collected from stagnant ponds in Hyderabad and identified morphologically. They were reared in glass containers containing dechlorinated water under laboratory-controlled conditions (27 ± 2 °C, 75–85% relative humidity, 14:10 h light/dark photoperiod). Larvae were fed daily with a mixture of dog biscuits and yeast in a 3:1 ratio until pupation. Pupae were transferred to emergence cages, and adults were maintained under the same conditions. Female mosquitoes were blood-fed on rodents to stimulate oviposition and colony establishment.

Formulation of Topical Creams

Two oil-in-water (O/W) emulsion cream formulations were prepared using the fusion method.

- **Test formulation:** contained 10% w/w EARR and 5% w/w *Eucalyptus globulus* oil.
- **Control formulation:** contained 5% w/w *Eucalyptus globulus* oil only.

Other excipients included stearic acid, cetostearyl alcohol, glycerin, potassium hydroxide,

methylparaben, and distilled water. The oil phase (stearic acid, cetostearyl alcohol, eucalyptus oil) and aqueous phase (glycerin, potassium hydroxide solution, methylparaben in distilled water) were separately heated to 70 °C. The aqueous phase was

slowly added to the oil phase with continuous stirring to form an emulsion. The resultant cream was cooled to room temperature, transferred into amber glass jars, and stored until evaluation.

Table: 1 Composition of herbal cream for mosquito repellent action

Ingredients	Formulation (% w/w)		Importance
	EARR +Eucalyptus cream	Eucalyptus cream	
<i>Asparagus racemosus extract</i>	10 %	-	Test compound
Eucalyptus oil	5 %	5 %	Natural essential oil repellent
Stearic acid	15%	15%	Emulsifying agent
Cetostearyl alcohol	5 %	5 %	Co-emulsifier
Glycerine	5 %	5 %	Humectant
Potassium hydroxide	0.5 %	0.5 %	Neutralizing agent for steric acid
Methyl paraben	0.2 %	0.2 %	Antimicrobial preservative
Distilled water (ml)	q.s	q.s	Diluent

The prepared topical cream formulations were tested for different physicochemical properties to check their quality and stability. The physical appearance (color, odor, and homogeneity) was observed visually to ensure uniform texture and no phase separation. The pH of the formulations was measured at 25 °C using a digital pH meter to confirm skin compatibility. The spread ability was evaluated by the slip and drag method, which shows how easily the cream spreads on a surface. This helps in assessing ease of application. The washability of the creams was checked by rinsing with distilled water to see how easily they could be removed from the skin. The viscosity was determined using a Brookfield viscometer to measure thickness and consistency of the formulations. Finally, stability studies were carried out under accelerated conditions (40 ± 2 °C, 75% RH) for 30 days. During this time, changes in appearance, pH, phase separation, and viscosity were monitored to evaluate stability of the creams.

Mosquito Repellent Efficacy

The repellent activity of the formulations was evaluated using the Arm-in-Cage (AIC) method in accordance with World Health Organization (WHO) guidelines (WHO, 2009). In this assay, healthy volunteers introduced their treated forearm into a cage containing 20 unfed female mosquitoes maintained under controlled laboratory conditions (27 ± 2 °C, 75–85% RH, and a 14:10 h light/dark cycle). The number of mosquito landings and bites on the treated arm was recorded at fixed time intervals and compared with those on an untreated control arm.

Figure 1: Arm-In-Cage Method

The percentage protection was calculated using the formula:

$$\text{Protection (\%)} = U (U-T) \times 100$$

where U = number of landings/bites on the untreated control and T = number on the treated arm.

The cream formulation containing EARR (10%) and eucalyptus oil (5%) exhibited a higher repellency rate, offering longer protection duration and significantly fewer mosquito landings compared to the control formulation with only eucalyptus oil.

Cockroach Repellent Formulation and Testing

Adult cockroaches were collected from local residential kitchens and bathrooms in Hyderabad, where infestation levels were observed to be moderate to high. Specimens were captured using

non-toxic sticky traps and carefully transferred to clean laboratory containers. Prior to experimentation, the cockroaches were acclimatized for 24 hours under laboratory conditions to minimize stress and standardize behavioral responses.

For the repellent study, a herbal spray formulation was prepared containing 10% ethanolic extract of *Asparagus racemosus* roots (EARR) and 5% eucalyptus oil. These active components were dispersed in 60% ethanol with the addition of 2% Tween 80 as a surfactant, and the final volume was adjusted to 100 mL with distilled water. A control spray formulation, without EARR, was prepared in the same manner.

All formulations were homogenized thoroughly, filtered through muslin cloth, and stored in amber-colored PET spray bottles to prevent phytochemical degradation due to light exposure.

Table 2: Composition of herbal cockroach repellent spray

Ingredients	Formulation (% w/w)		Importance
	EARR +Eucalyptus spray	Eucalyptus spray	
<i>Asparagus racemosus</i> extract	10 %	-	Testcompound
Eucalyptus oil	5 %	5 %	Natural essential oil repellent
Ethanol (95%)	60 %	60 %	Solvent
Tween 80	2 %	2 %	Surfactant
Distilled water (ml)	q.s	q.s	Diluent

Evaluation of Cockroach Repellent Sprays

The prepared cockroach repellent sprays were subjected to physicochemical evaluation. Visual inspection was carried out to assess clarity, homogeneity, and phase separation, while the pH was measured using a digital pH meter to ensure suitability for both skin contact and household surface applications. Both formulations exhibited good physical stability during storage, with no signs of sedimentation, odor alteration, or phase

separation. The incorporation of Tween 80 as a surfactant enhanced emulsion stability and facilitated uniform dispersion of eucalyptus oil within the ethanolic extract. These findings confirmed that the EARR-based spray maintained its physical integrity and was appropriate for domestic use.

Repellent efficacy was evaluated using the two-choice chamber method. A rectangular arena was divided into two equal zones, with one surface treated with the test formulation and the other left

untreated as control. A group of 10–15 healthy adult cockroaches was released at the center of the arena, and their movement patterns were monitored over a period of 15–60 minutes. The number of cockroaches present in each zone was recorded, and the percentage repellency was calculated using the formula:

$$\text{Repellency (\%)} = \frac{N_c (N_c - N_t)}{N_c} \times 100$$

where N_c represents the number of cockroaches in the control zone and N_t represents the number in the treated zone.

The formulation containing EARR (10%) and eucalyptus oil (5%) demonstrated strong repellency (>80%), which was significantly higher compared to the eucalyptus-only spray, confirming its superior efficacy for household pest management.

Molecular Docking and Statistical Analysis

Molecular docking studies were carried out using CB-Dock2 to predict the binding interactions of selected phytoconstituents from *Asparagus racemosus* with insect acetylcholine receptors (AChRs), which are critical for neural signaling and survival. Inhibition or disruption of AChRs interferes with normal neurotransmission, thereby contributing to insecticidal and repellent effects. AutoDock Vina was employed to calculate binding affinities, where more negative Vina scores indicated stronger ligand–receptor interactions.

All experimental data from the in vivo repellent assays—including the Arm-in-Cage test for mosquitoes and the Two-choice chamber test for cockroaches—were subjected to statistical analysis. Results were expressed as Mean \pm Standard Deviation (SD) from three independent replicates ($n = 3$). A two-way Analysis of Variance

(ANOVA) was performed to determine the individual and interactive effects of time and formulation on repellent efficacy. Statistical significance was accepted at $p < 0.05$. Data analysis and graphical representations were carried out using GraphPad Prism version 9.0 (GraphPad Software, San Diego, USA).

RESULTS

The percentage yield of the *Asparagus racemosus* ethanolic extract was found to be 18% w/w. Preliminary phytochemical screening confirmed the presence of diverse bioactive compounds including alkaloids, flavonoids, saponin glycosides, tannins, steroids, triterpenoids, amino acids, carbohydrates, fats and fixed oils, proteins, and starch, which may contribute to the pharmacological and repellent properties of the plant.

Quantitative estimation showed that the total phenolic content of the extract was 5.419 mg gallic acid equivalents (GAE)/g of dried root, as determined from the gallic acid calibration curve ($y = 0.0026x + 0.5491$, $R^2 = 0.9697$). The total flavonoid content was 3.515 mg quercetin equivalents (QE)/g, calculated from the quercetin standard curve ($y = 0.002x - 0.0043$, $R^2 = 0.9914$). GC-MS analysis revealed several phytoconstituents, including methyl sulfidtirole, xanthone, oxirane, n-hexadecanoic acid, flavone, 1,8-nonadiene, epoxyhexanol, pentadecane-2,4-dione, and stigmaterol.

Herbal cream formulations prepared with *A. racemosus* root extract and eucalyptus oil, and a control cream with eucalyptus oil alone, were assessed for physicochemical parameters. Both formulations displayed smooth and homogeneous textures without evidence of phase separation. The pH values were 6.2 ± 0.1 for the test cream and 6.1 ± 0.2 for the control, which fall within the

acceptable range for topical application. Both formulations exhibited satisfactory spreadability and washability, although the test cream showed slightly reduced spreadability. The viscosity values were $22,500 \pm 300$ cP (test cream) and $21,800 \pm 350$ cP (control), consistent with desirable topical cream properties. Stability testing under accelerated conditions (40 ± 2 °C, $75 \pm 5\%$ RH) for four weeks revealed no significant changes in pH, color, odor, or consistency, confirming the stability of both creams.

The mosquito repellent efficacy, determined using the Arm-in-Cage method, demonstrated superior

activity of the *A. racemosus* + eucalyptus cream compared to the eucalyptus-only cream. At 30 minutes post-application, the test cream achieved 81.32% repellency versus 71.43% for the control. Repellency decreased progressively over time, but the test cream maintained 50.00% repellency at 120 minutes, compared to 31.33% for the control. At 180 minutes, repellency values declined to 33.11% (test cream) and 11.92% (control), indicating that while efficacy reduced over time, the *A. racemosus* formulation provided longer-lasting protection.

Table 3: Repellent Efficacy of Herbal and Eucalyptus Creams in Arm-in-Cage Mosquito Test

Time (min)	Control Landings (Mean \pm SD)	EARR + Eucalyptus Cream Landings (Mean \pm SD)	EARR + Eucalyptus % Repellency	Eucalyptus Cream Landings (Mean \pm SD)	Eucalyptus cream % Repellency
0	0.0 \pm 0.0	0.0 \pm 0.0	-	0.0 \pm 0.0	-
30	18.2 \pm 0.4	3.4 \pm 0.6	81.32%	5.2 \pm 0.7	71.43%
60	17.7 \pm 0.6	4.8 \pm 0.7	72.88%	6.9 \pm 0.6	61.02%
90	17.2 \pm 0.5	7.5 \pm 0.5	56.40%	9.3 \pm 0.8	45.93%
120	16.6 \pm 0.6	8.3 \pm 0.8	50.00%	11.4 \pm 0.9	31.33%
150	15.4 \pm 0.5	9.7 \pm 0.9	37.01%	12.7 \pm 1.0	17.53%
180	15.1 \pm 0.4	10.1 \pm 0.7	33.11%	13.3 \pm 0.8	11.92%

(Mean \pm SD, n = 20 mosquitoes per trial)

Figure 2: Comparison of Percentage Mosquito Repellency between Herbal Cream (*Asparagus racemosus* + Eucalyptus) and Eucalyptus Alone Cream Over Time

Similarly, evaluation of the cockroach repellent sprays showed that both the herbal and control formulations produced stable emulsions with acceptable clarity and sprayability. The herbal spray containing *A. racemosus* extract and eucalyptus oil demonstrated a maximum

repellency of 77.89% at 30 minutes, significantly higher than the control. At the peak repellency point, the number of cockroach entries in the treated area was only 4.2 ± 0.7 . Although repellency declined with time, it remained statistically significant across the 180-minute

study. At 90 minutes, repellency was 53.93%, and it persisted at 27.04% after 180 minutes, underscoring its potential for prolonged household application. Physicochemical evaluation of both

sprays, including pH, viscosity, spray delivery rate, and mist pattern, confirmed their suitability for indoor use.

Table 4: Repellent Efficacy of Herbal and Eucalyptus spray in Two choice chamber for cockroach repellent Test

Time (min)	Control Entries (Mean ± SD)	EARR + Eucalyptus Spray Entries (Mean ± SD)	EARR + Eucalyptus Repellency %	Eucalyptus Spray Entries (Mean ± SD)	Eucalyptus Repellency %
0	0.0 ± 0.0	0.0 ± 0.0	-	0.0 ± 0.0	-
30	19.0 ± 0.6	4.2 ± 0.7	77.89%	6.1 ± 0.8	67.89%
60	18.5 ± 0.7	5.7 ± 0.6	69.19%	8.3 ± 0.6	55.14%
90	17.8 ± 0.5	8.2 ± 0.8	53.93%	10.7 ± 0.7	39.88%
120	17.1 ± 0.6	9.3 ± 0.7	45.61%	12.8 ± 0.9	25.15%
150	16.5 ± 0.6	10.8 ± 0.9	34.55%	13.7 ± 0.8	16.97%
180	15.9 ± 0.5	11.6 ± 0.8	27.04%	14.5 ± 0.6	8.81%

(Mean± SD, n = 20 cockroaches per trial)

Figure 3: EARR + Eucalyptus sprayed paper in left side chamber and control treatment in right side at 30 minutes.

Figure 4: Eucalyptus sprayed paper in right side chamber and control treatment in the left side at 30 minutes.

Molecular docking studies were performed to investigate the potential interactions of key phytoconstituents from *Asparagus racemosus* root extract (EARR) with insect acetylcholinesterase (AChE), a critical enzyme in the nervous system. Compounds such as stigmasterol, asparanin B, shatavarin I, flavone, and n-hexadecanoic acid were docked using CB-Dock2 and analyzed with AutoDock Vina. The docking results revealed that stigmasterol and asparanin B exhibited the strongest binding affinities, with Vina scores of -11.6 and -11.5, respectively, indicating high potential for AChE inhibition. Other compounds, including shatavarin I and flavone, also demonstrated significant binding interactions, suggesting that multiple constituents may contribute synergistically to neuroinhibition. The binding poses showed stable interactions within the active site of AChE, including hydrogen bonding and hydrophobic interactions, which likely disrupt normal neurotransmission in insects. These findings support the hypothesis that the repellent activity observed in vivo against mosquitoes and cockroaches may be mediated, at least in part, through the neurotoxic effects of EARR phytoconstituents.

Figure 5: Molecular analysis of the binding affinities and receptor interaction of the selected active compounds toward the hub target Acetyl Choline Esterase (1EEA).

DISCUSSION

The present study explored the phytomedicinal potential of *Asparagus racemosus* root extract (EARR) in the development of herbal formulations for repellent activity against mosquitoes (*Aedes aegypti*) and cockroaches (*Periplaneta americana*). Outcomes from phytochemical screening, GC-MS profiling, formulation development, biological assays, and molecular docking collectively support the hypothesis that EARR possesses bioactive constituents responsible for significant repellent effects.

The preliminary phytochemical screening confirmed the presence of flavonoids, alkaloids, saponin glycosides, steroids, amino acids, and carbohydrates. These secondary metabolites are well documented for their insecticidal and repellent roles. For example, flavonoids and alkaloids in *Azadirachta indica* (Neem) and *Cymbopogon citratus* (Lemongrass) have been reported to possess strong insect-repelling activity (Koul et al., 2008; Pavela, 2015). GC-MS analysis of EARR further revealed compounds such as stigmasterol, flavone, n-hexadecanoic acid, xanthosine, and asparanin B. Many of these

metabolites are known for biological activities including repellency, oviposition deterrence, or enzyme inhibition. Stigmasterol and palmitic acid, for instance, have been shown to possess larvicidal and oviposition-deterrent effects against *Anopheles stephensi* and *Aedes aegypti* (Govindarajan et al., 2016; Benelli et al., 2017).

Quantitative estimation of total phenolics (5.419 mg GAE/g) and flavonoids (3.515 mg QE/g) confirmed the antioxidant richness of the extract. Phenolics and flavonoids are associated with insect-repellent action through mechanisms such as disruption of olfactory signaling, neurotoxicity, and deterrent feeding behavior. Similar findings were reported by Isman (2006) and Sukumar et al. (1991), who demonstrated that plant phenolics could function as semiochemicals interfering with mosquito host-seeking behavior.

The herbal mosquito repellent cream and cockroach repellent spray prepared with EARR and eucalyptus oil exhibited favorable physicochemical properties, including stability, spreadability, viscosity, and pH compatibility, confirming their suitability for topical and indoor applications. Comparable stability and user-acceptability results were reported for herbal creams formulated with *Ocimum sanctum* and essential oils (Senthilkumar & Varma, 2017). In the arm-in-cage assay, the EARR + eucalyptus cream demonstrated superior repellency compared to eucalyptus alone. At 30 minutes, the repellency was 81.32% compared to 71.43%, and this advantage persisted over 180 minutes, with significant efficacy ($p < 0.05$) up to 120 minutes. The enhanced and prolonged activity suggests synergistic or additive effects of EARR phytoconstituents with eucalyptus oil. Similar synergism between plant extracts and essential oils was reported for *Ocimum sanctum* formulations

providing prolonged mosquito repellency (Chokechaijaroenporn et al., 1994).

The two-choice chamber assay against *Periplaneta americana* also confirmed the enhanced efficacy of the herbal spray. At 30 minutes, the EARR + eucalyptus spray showed 77.89% repellency compared to 67.89% for eucalyptus alone, and this benefit persisted until 180 minutes, with 27.04% repellency compared to 8.81% for eucalyptus. These results indicate a prolonged deterrent effect attributable to the extract. Appel and Tanley (2000) similarly reported longer-lasting cockroach repellency using combined plant extracts, such as *Lantana camara* and *Eucalyptus globulus*.

Molecular docking studies revealed that stigmasterol, shatavarin I, and asparanin B exhibited strong binding affinities with insect acetylcholinesterase (AChE), with Vina scores of -11.6 and -11.5 . Inhibition of AChE disrupts neurotransmission and motor coordination, producing neurotoxic effects that manifest as repellency. Comparable docking outcomes were reported by Walia et al. (2017), where plant-derived steroids showed strong affinities with insect AChE, thereby validating their insecticidal potential.

Collectively, the findings confirm that EARR, especially in combination with eucalyptus oil, offers significant and prolonged repellent efficacy against both mosquitoes and cockroaches. The phytochemical richness, validated biological assays, and molecular docking outcomes highlight its potential as a botanical source for eco-friendly repellents. Moreover, this study supports the traditional knowledge of *Asparagus racemosus* through modern scientific validation, positioning it as a sustainable alternative to synthetic chemical repellents.

CONCLUSION

The present investigation confirms that *Asparagus racemosus* root extract (EARR), when combined with eucalyptus oil, exhibits significant insect-repellent activity against both mosquitoes and cockroaches. The herbal formulations demonstrated high repellency during the initial observation periods, reaching 81.32% against mosquitoes and 77.89% against cockroaches at 30 minutes, and maintained moderate efficacy for up to 180 minutes. Phytochemical screening and GC-MS analysis identified several bioactive constituents, including stigmasterol, flavone, n-hexadecanoic acid, asparanin B, and shatavarin I, which are known to contribute to insecticidal or repellent activities. Molecular docking further confirmed strong binding affinities of these compounds, particularly stigmasterol and asparanin B, with insect acetylcholinesterase, suggesting a neuroinhibitory mechanism underlying the observed repellency. Collectively, these results validate *A. racemosus* as a promising botanical source for the development of safe, effective, and eco-friendly insect repellent formulations, thereby offering a sustainable alternative to synthetic chemical repellents.

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HOW TO CITE: Namburu Sree Lakshmi, Pratap Veeresh Babu, T Venkata Shiva Sai Karthik, Nalluri Kavya Sri, Jagannagari Eshwar, Evaluation of *Asparagus racemosus* Root Extract and Eucalyptus Oil Formulations as Plant-Based Repellents Against Mosquitoes and Cockroaches, *Int. J. of Pharm. Sci.*, 2025, Vol 3, Issue 9, 3082-3093. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17203151>

